

THE ROLE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN LEARNING FOREIGN
LANGUAGES

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the use of information technologies in teaching foreign languages. In comparison with the traditional methods used in previous studies, it is described that learning using information technologies has a number of advantages, and their use in early childhood increased the features of thinking and perception of the younger generation who grew up in the environment of modern digital means.

Keywords. information technologies, computer programs, gadgets, internet, multimedia

Currently, knowledge of one of the foreign languages allows the younger generation to join the world culture of a modern person, communicate with friends, relatives and colleagues living in foreign countries, as well as study at higher educational institutions of foreign countries, participate in various competitions and grants, learn news from magazines published in foreign languages in their specialty.

We live in the age of information technology, when a modern teenager is a productive and active user of social networks, mobile applications, computer programs and gadgets.

If we talk about the educational sphere, a modern teacher uses computer technologies, of course, in order to create an opportunity to convey lessons from the subject he teaches in an interesting, easy and understandable way to the audience, to increase the professional competence of the teacher and to expand the range of subjects taught.

Computer technologies provide an opportunity for the development of society, in particular, for the younger generation to acquire modern knowledge, regularly receive information from world news, have additional information on the subject from the Internet, without relying solely on textbooks when completing assigned tasks. Currently, computer technologies penetrate into all spheres of human activity and form a global information space. Knowledge of languages and computer technologies is one of the important factors in the level of education of any modern specialist.

Nowadays, the rapid development of information technology leads to the emergence of new ways of using the Internet. All over the world, there is a dynamic and rapid construction of an information society, which creates the best conditions for personal growth of a person. The main reason for this process is the strong development of information technology.

In the 21st century, the educational process is increasingly developing the organization of training using information technology.

Professor E. S. Polat says about this: "New pedagogical technologies... firstly, it is unthinkable without the widespread use of new information technologies, computer technologies", since they "fully reveal the pedagogical, didactic functions of these methods, allowing them to realize their inherent potential"

As in all spheres of society, the use of information technology in the medical field, in particular, the use of multimedia technologies, is becoming an integral part of the professional activity of a teacher every day.

The use of information technology plays an important role in the process of teaching foreign languages, especially to students of medical universities. Today, the use of various multimedia

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technologies makes the process of learning foreign languages interesting and accessible to the student, allowing him to adequately understand the subject being transmitted.

The use of computer technology helps to remove the psychological barrier of the student, which is the way of using a foreign language as a means of communication. One of the manifestations of this barrier is the fear of making a mistake. When students use a computer, they do not feel discomfort, they receive instructions on how to cope with the mistakes they make.

Systematic work with computer tasks forms students' sustainable skills for independent completion, which leads to a reduction in the time allotted by the teacher to complete assigned tasks and allows you to increase the time needed to complete creative work. But at the same time, the integration of students into the use of information technology in the educational process places great demands not only on the student, but also on the teacher.

Careful use of information technology by students of higher educational institutions creates a lot of conveniences for them in mastering specialized subjects, as well as foreign languages. In particular, the ability of students to use information technology, especially the Internet, allows them to receive additional information on the topic specified in their specialties, find solutions to problems, easily understand textbooks, journals and scientific articles published abroad. At the same time, independent learning will help them prepare presentations on topics.

One of the most important reserves for increasing the effectiveness of training at a university is the optimization of independent work of students. Therefore, in the context of computerization of education and due to the fact that academic hours for studying a foreign language in medical institutions are limited, students can fill in the gaps in their knowledge of a foreign language only via the Internet.

Students will be able to find solutions to the problems they encounter using the Internet, learn to move freely in the field of a foreign language, solve emerging problems, which in turn will create an opportunity to increase their creativity.

One of the most important factors is the teacher's preparation for classes, the distribution of materials by topic - cards, tables, tests; visual materials, information technology in the preparation of presentations. Preparing presentations and including them in the educational process is a new didactic tool. Presentations are aimed at developing students' interest in science, motivation, interactivity, increasing their creative potential.

Based on my personal activities, I can say that I use multimedia presentations that include great opportunities for developing the mental and creative abilities of students who teach, in each of my classes. When I explained the topic to students in a simple way, that is, on the board, I looked at the shock that their activity in the training would slow down, or rather, when I explained the topic in a prepared presentation, their interests, activity would increase several times. They will have the opportunity to demonstrate organizational skills, hidden talents. Develops interests in language, imagination, creative thinking and independence.

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of various means of information technology in foreign language lessons helps to increase students' interest in the subject and the effective formulation of all types of speech activity, as well as the formation of sustainable skills of independent work.

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